

Digital Transformation Investment Towards Green Economy in Vietnam

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ABSTRACT

Economic growth is the goal of countries worldwide, with sustainable development being the ultimate way to achieve this goal. This is why many scholars believe that one way of achieving an economy is to direct business operations towards digitalization. The goal of the present article is to set on the course of transformation of enterprises in the context of building an economy and somewhat study the reality of how digital transformation in Vietnamese enterprises is to be facilitated for the coming period. Through documentary research, evidence is provided that companies are currently digitizing business operations to realize a green economy; however, there seem to be a few shortcomings in the implementation process.

1. INTRODUCTION

In many activities of many industries in Vietnam, especially with the rapid development of technology as part of the Industrial Revolution 4.0, the daily adoption of digital technologies, including AI, big data, IoT, and blockchain, provides many opportunities to improve efficiency in production and service quality and enhance the competitiveness of enterprises. At the same time, the world is not only changing in terms of digital transformation, but also developing a green economy - an orientation that many countries are aiming to identify because this development trend does not cause negative impacts on the environment and also helps ensure sustainable development.

For many years, countries have run a "brown" economy pursuing economic growth in terms of quantity and breadth without attaching importance to quality growth. The natural result is the rapid loss of natural resources along with increasing emissions and pollution, severely destroying the ecological environment and causing global warming and climate change in ways that endanger human life and all forms of existence. Furthermore, by consuming too many resources today, future generations may have limited access to them, thus affecting the process of sustainable development. In this regard, countries are under pressure to change their economic models to ensure the more efficient and environmentally safe use of natural resources. A common agreement among countries regarding a truly "green" economy exists to describe the concept of sustainable development. In the view of many scholars, it is at this moment of the Fourth Industrial Revolution that the optimal

way, that is, digital transformation, to green the economy appears.

Digital transformation brings many breakthrough applications to businesses, thereby changing the economic model towards more efficiency, better quality, and greener, as well as some positive externalities. Many scholars have affirmed the role of digital transformation in green economic development. According to Lijuan and Yan (2024), digital transformation plays a positive role and directly spreads to green economic efficiency by promoting green structural transformation, energy efficiency, and increasing public concern about the environment. As Li et al. (2024) state, digital technology holds a key position in the modern economy. Accordingly, information and communication technology effectively improve green total factor productivity through technological progress, energy intensity, and trade openness, and can contribute to promoting green economic efficiency. Therefore, it can be affirmed that digital transformation in enterprises is an important factor promoting the development of the green economy.

Digital transformation, with advanced technologies such as artificial intelligence, big data, and the Internet of Things, has the potential to help a region build a sustainable green economy. Applying digital technology to resource management, environmental monitoring, and production optimization will minimize negative impacts on the environment and promote eco-friendly production. Simultaneously, digital transformation also helps improve the competitiveness of businesses in the region, thereby supporting sustainable economic development. Therefore,

researching and implementing digital transformation towards a green economy in Vietnam is necessary to meet urgent practical requirements and contribute to sustainable development in the region.

2. CLARIFYING SOME DEFINITIONS

Digital Transformation

In the era of Industry 4.0, digital technology is becoming increasingly important in all areas of the economy, life, and society. Following Siebel (2019), the content of digital transformation is the integration of four breakthrough technologies: cloud computing, big data, IoT, and artificial intelligence. Such integration makes the scope of the application of digital transformation very wide. It has been applied in many fields to make a difference. As reported by Feng et al. (2022), digital transformation includes strategic and enterprise digital transformation. Strategic Digital Transformation emphasizes significant changes in the national governance mechanism, reorienting the economy to have new breakthroughs and invigorating the framework of industries, jobs, and society in a better direction to increase economic and social welfare for the people. Strategic digital transformation also emphasizes the reconfiguration of business models and formation of corporate cultures based on leaders' ambitions. Enterprise digitalization emphasizes the application of digital technology to business processes and production systems to optimize production and business operations, improve productivity, enhance economic value, and create new values to meet new human needs. Warner and Wager (2019) share the same view that digitalization is the process of interweaving advanced digital technologies with core business connections to drive innovation in production methods and business processes, as well as restructuring business models to improve business efficiency and enable business empowerment and transformation. Paperless technology transformation involves the implementation of disruptive technology to increase productivity, creative value, and social welfare.

Green Economy

Due to the depletion of natural resources and increasingly serious environmental pollution, which can cause death to people around the world, the concept of "green economy" has become the orientation and goal of the national economy. The term 'green economy' was first introduced in the report by Pearce et al. (1989). In accordance with UNDESA (2012), the United Nations has reiterated the call for the concept of "green economy" as a way out in the context of the world economic crisis. There are many definitions of "green economy."

According to the European Commission (2010), green economies develop intelligently, sustainably, and fairly. According to the Green Economy Alliance (2012), a green economy creates a better quality of life for everyone within the ecological limits of Earth.

The International Chamber of Commerce has defined a Green Economy as one in which economic growth and environmental responsibility go hand in hand and are mutually reinforced while supporting social development (ICC, 2012).

Based on the United Nations Environment Programme, a Green Economy works for human well-being and social equity, while reducing major risks to the environment and ecosystems. It includes low-carbon resource use and efficient and equitable societies (UNEP 2011).

In Vietnam, in accordance with Decision No. 1658/QĐ-TTg dated October 1, 2021, of the Prime Minister approving the National Strategy on Green Growth for the period 2021–2030, with a vision to 2050, a green economy is defined as an economy that ensures sustainable economic growth, in which growth and development are not only based on GDP growth but also focus on environmental protection and ensuring social equity. A green economy aims to minimize negative impacts on the environment through environmentally friendly development activities, efficient use of natural resources, reduction of greenhouse gas emissions, promotion of clean technology, and sustainable production. At the same time, a green economy also focuses on improving quality of life, creating green jobs, and promoting social inclusion, contributing to sustainable development and ensuring social security. This decision emphasizes that a green economy is an important part of the green growth strategy, aiming to achieve the dual goal of sustainable economic development and protection and improvement of the natural environment.

Regarding the implications of the above definitions, "green economy" must include the contents of economic development, social development, and environmental protection. Comparing the implications of "green economy" and "sustainable development," it can be said that "green economy" also cares about three aspects: economic - social and environmental. However, "green economy" first focuses on economic - environmental, and then, based on that foundation, promotes human prosperity and social equity. Therefore, it can be said that "green economy" is the inevitable path to sustainable development.

The Role of Digital Transformation in the Green Economy

Digital transformation involves the use of advances in digital technology, directed towards economic management processes and all business activities to increase output as well as resource efficiency, thereby reducing the negative impact of all of these on the environment/ecosystem and ensuring sustainable economic growth in general, which is what is called digital transformation. In this case, digital transformation can be seen as a way out for businesses to optimize control/management and production processes, improve productivity, reduce internal and external cost needs, and reduce energy consumption (Han & Liu, 2022). In addition, according to Bartel et al. (2007), the application of digital technology aims to innovate production processes, products, and skills for workers. The results show that the

Internet facilitates collaboration among R&D, design, and manufacturing firms, thus creating new forms of business.

Technological progress is an important driving force for the development of a green economy through innovations in production technology related to the use of clean energy and resources, creating more environmentally friendly production processes, and improving total green factor productivity. Digital transformation enhances management capabilities and promotes improved environments for sustainable business operations. This is the process of using the latest technology to perform management tasks to coordinate business activities. It helps enhance synergies in the workplace through higher efficiency with minimal harm to the environment. The technological development of digital technology helps reduce the energy intensity of enterprises through technological innovation and production technology, using energy-saving and environmentally friendly technologies and equipment to reduce energy costs, improve production efficiency, increase total green factor productivity, and save energy (Feng et al., 2018).

Han et al. (2023) found that digital transformation through artificial intelligence, cloud computing, and big data technology in heavily polluting enterprises can significantly improve total green factor productivity owing to green innovation, management efficiency, and reduction of external transaction costs. Digital technology will be smarter in collecting information and providing knowledge to all stakeholders to improve their production processes and products for optimization, automation, and environmental pollution reduction.

Wang et al. (2024) pointed out that the Internet is an essential factor in green economic development processes. Consequently, the Internet can promote industrial structure upgrading, accelerate enterprise innovation, and indirectly promote green economic growth. Meanwhile, Chen et al. (2023) demonstrated that ensuring that the manufacturing industry undergoes digital transformation will help them address environmental concerns. This will ultimately reduce the burden on natural resources and, in turn, support the development of a green economy. Wang et al. (2024) also showed that the digital transformation process through three factors—government investment, technology integration, and public concern for the environment—significantly improved green resilience. Pollution emissions are limited during the digital transformation process. The study confirmed that a reduction in energy consumption in the production of goods improves green resilience because digital transformation leads to improved energy efficiency.

Using digital technology platforms, city managers can easily understand urban energy consumption and environmental pollution. This will facilitate the design of scientific strategies for energy consumption and environmental protection. In addition, such digital technology applications will perform analysis and forecasting of environmental problems. This

provides authorities with a basis for developing policies to improve environmental quality.

Through digital transformation, businesses can understand consumer preferences more accurately and adjust their production and marketing methods to match market demand, helping increase their market share. More importantly, green resilience can be enhanced by facilitating the development of Green Technology through digital platforms to create Green Innovation in many fields. In general, digital transformation can intervene in every business activity to improve business efficiency, optimize input resources, and minimize environmental damage by bringing prosperity to everyone.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The author applies a desk research method through which information and big data are collected from sources such as legal documents, topics, and works in journals related to digital transformation and green economy. The author constructs and critically analyzes the nature of the definitions of digital transformation, digital transformation of enterprises, and green economy, as well as the role of digital transformation of enterprises in green economic development. In addition, the author studies the characteristics of the current digital transformation of enterprises in Vietnam.

4. RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Government of Vietnam has issued a number of legal documents, including Resolution No. 52-NQ/TW, dated September 27, 2019, on a number of directives and policies to proactively participate in the Fourth Industrial Revolution by 2030, building a Vietnamese digital government by developing a digital economy accounting for 30% of GDP and ranking 3rd in e-government and digital economy among ASEAN countries. Decision No. 749/QĐ-TTg, dated June 3, 2020, of the Prime Minister promulgated the National Digital Transformation Program to 2025, with a vision to 2030, builds fundamental tasks to develop six more digital transformation solutions: raising awareness, building institutions, developing digital infrastructure, developing digital platforms, creating trust (national leaders), ensuring network safety and security, international cooperation, research and development, and innovative actions in all dimensions of the digital environment. Document No. 1658/QĐ-TTg dated October 1, 2021, of the Prime Minister on the "National Strategy on Green Growth for the 2021-2030 period, with a vision to 2050" considers green growth as the main goal of the strategy, emphasizing the link between economic restructuring and growth model innovation, enhancing competitiveness and resilience to external shocks. Green growth depends on sound institutions and governance, advanced science and technology, and investment flows towards green growth in the application of advanced technology, digital transformation, and smart and sustainable infrastructure. Vietnamese enterprises operating in many

fields have strongly promoted the application of digital transformation in management activities, production, marketing, sales, warehousing, and payment.

As reported by a survey in Vietnam by the World Bank (2020), the Internet of Things (IoT) is the most widely applied technology in Vietnam in agriculture, smart homes, healthcare, and industrial production. In agricultural production, IoT promotes precision and smart farming, covering all stages from planting and raising livestock to irrigation, harvesting, storage, distribution, and marketing of agricultural products. In this way, the added value in the agricultural sector increases while contributing to reducing labor intensity, conserving water resources, and improving management and farm care capacity, thereby promoting farming efficiency, productivity, and quality of agricultural products while improving environmental quality compared to traditional agricultural activities to produce organic agricultural products to serve the green living needs of people towards a green economy.

In industrial production, factories are equipped with smart sensors in production lines, product inventory, product quality monitoring, machine maintenance, etc. to help managers control business situations. Timely measurement improves production efficiency and saves costs in the process of greening the economy. Many Vietnamese enterprises have applied automation (robots), artificial intelligence (AI), embedded devices, and software such as MES and ERP to improve operational management efficiency. It saves costs, increases customers, and improves supply chain integrity.

In the medical field, the IoT allows health monitoring and diagnosis. Many hospitals have deployed remote medical examination and treatment applications, online appointment booking, and electronic prescriptions. The above helps reduce overload in hospitals or other medical facilities and limits contact in situations where the disease can spread (cross-infection) because of the large number of people. In addition, such e-prescription applications will help contact doctors quickly and efficiently, thereby reducing their travel costs and time.

The strategy of deploying IoT applications with banking services to enable and access the use of those services by customers and connecting supported customers with other digital ecosystems available on the Internet platform or banking services through applications installed directly on mobile phones...

Technology-based ride-hailing services are strongly developed in the transportation industry using digital technology platforms to improve customer experience.

Through digital transformation, the education industry has led to the development of online learning platforms, platforms for managing and sharing lecture resources and learning materials, and digitizing textbooks, documents, etc. This contributes to reducing the use of paper and traveling towards a green economy.

Many large corporations in the retail market, such as VinGroup, have diverse customer bases. Therefore, they have developed a unified customer management system (VinID) that allows customers to integrate and manage information while transacting with VinGroup in many different services, such as paying bills, electricity bills, and shopping.

Many retail businesses have applied software and solutions for multi-channel management, distribution channel management, and online sales on e-commerce platforms such as Shopee and Tiki; marketing on platforms such as Facebook, Google, and Tiktok; and using software to support accounting activities and customer care.

Digital transformation applications have helped companies save input costs, improve product and service quality to achieve sustainable economic growth, continue to contribute to reducing the use of natural resources and emissions, be environmentally friendly, and comply with the requirements of a green economy. This enables a higher quality of products and services in the economy thanks to digital transformation, bringing “better” life to everyone.

5. CHALLENGES AND SOLUTIONS FOR DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION TOWARDS A GREEN ECONOMY IN VIETNAM

Digital transformation towards a green economy in Vietnam is a necessary and urgent goal to address the challenges of sustainable development in the context of increasingly serious climate change and environmental problems. However, this process faces many major challenges in terms of technology, infrastructure, human resources, and finances. These challenges require not only the efforts of businesses and people but also strong support from state and international organizations to ensure effective and sustainable transformation.

First, there is a lack of technology infrastructure and digital networks. One of the biggest challenges for digital transformation in Vietnam is the lack of technology infrastructure and digital networks. This area is mainly rural, with many remote areas, making the deployment of the internet and technology infrastructure more difficult than in urban areas. Poor Internet infrastructure not only makes it difficult for businesses to access modern technologies, but also hinders the implementation of smart solutions such as environmental monitoring systems, resource management, and product traceability. This significantly affects the ability to apply digital technology in agricultural, aquatic, and industrial production activities in the region.

Second, there is a lack of financial resources and difficulties in investment: digital transformation requires a large initial investment cost, from purchasing equipment to upgrading systems and training human resources. However, most businesses in Vietnam are small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), which often do not have sufficient financing to invest in technology. Solutions such as IoT systems in smart agriculture, big data analysis technologies,

and environmental monitoring applications all require high costs, which is a major barrier for businesses. In addition, access to preferential credit packages or support from financial institutions is still limited, making it difficult for many businesses to implement digital transformation projects comprehensively.

Third, there is a lack of skilled and qualified human resources; digital transformation not only requires technology but also requires human resources with appropriate skills and qualifications. However, Vietnam lacks highly specialized human resources in the fields of information technology and digital transformation. Businesses here have difficulty recruiting and retaining technology experts, especially those with knowledge of new technologies, such as artificial intelligence, big data, and the Internet of Things. This shortage reduces the effectiveness of the process of implementing digital solutions, making it difficult for businesses to effectively and sustainably carry out digital transformation.

Fourth, enterprises have limited awareness and skills. Another challenge is that the awareness and skills of enterprises regarding digital transformation are still limited. Many enterprises do not really understand the benefits of implementing digital transformation in their production and business activities. The lack of understanding of new technologies and their applications has led to the ineffective application of digital transformation, reducing the competitiveness of enterprises. In addition, enterprises are unfamiliar with green standards and environmental protection requirements, leading to difficulties in implementing green economic activities and protecting natural resources.

Fifth, the challenge of synchronization between localities: Vietnam includes many provinces and cities with different socio-economic conditions; therefore, implementing digital transformation synchronously and consistently between localities is a big challenge. Each locality has different levels of infrastructure development, resources, and management capacity; therefore, the application of technology is uneven. The lack of coordination between provinces and cities and the lack of a comprehensive digital development strategy cause the digital transformation process to face many obstacles. This makes it more difficult to build a common green economic system for the entire region, because localities do not have the same consistent and synchronous development direction.

Sixth, the impact of climate change and environmental issues: Vietnam is heavily affected by climate change, with problems such as saline intrusion, landslides, and prolonged drought. These issues not only affect production activities but also increase the costs and difficulties in implementing digital solutions. For example, environmental monitoring devices or IoT systems in agriculture may malfunction when faced with extreme weather conditions, thereby affecting the process of data collection and effective monitoring. Simultaneously, having to deal with environmental issues also makes

businesses consider using financial resources more, instead of investing in digital transformation.

Seventh, the lack of specific support policies from the state: Although the state has policies to encourage digital transformation and green economic development, the implementation of these policies still lacks synchronization and specificity. Enterprises still have difficulty accessing financial support packages, human resource training programs, and green standards guidelines. In particular, the lack of tax incentives or funding for enterprises investing in green technology does not motivate them to drastically implement digital transformation. This requires a specific policy framework suitable for socio-economic characteristics to comprehensively promote digital transformation and a green economy.

Solutions to overcome challenges

To overcome these challenges, there needs to be close coordination between the state, enterprises, and the international community. First, the development of technology infrastructure and Internet networks is urgent, especially in rural, remote, and isolated areas. The government needs to step up investments in digital infrastructure to ensure that all businesses and individuals have access to new technologies.

Additionally, there should be appropriate financial support programs, such as preferential credit packages or innovation support funds, to help businesses easily invest in digital transformation. At the same time, it is also important to strengthen human resource training and raise awareness of digital transformation. Training programs on information technology skills, data management, and environmental protection should be organized to help local human resources prepare for the digital transformation process.

In addition, it is necessary to develop preferential tax policies and support businesses in carrying out green economic activities while strengthening international cooperation to acquire advanced models and technologies. Coordination between localities in the region also needs to be promoted to create a synchronous and effective digital transformation and green economy strategy.

Digital transformation towards a green economy is a long and challenging road, but this is also an opportunity for Vietnam to develop sustainably and adapt to climate change. Overcoming these challenges will not only help the region develop more strongly but also contribute to the country's sustainable development goals.

6. POLICY IMPLICATIONS

To promote digital transformation towards a green economy, the government and businesses need to have specific policies and strategies that are suitable to the characteristics of the region and the actual situation. The following are the proposed policy implications for both the government and businesses to overcome challenges in the digital transformation process and promote a green economy:

Policy implications for the government

Developing synchronous digital infrastructure: The government needs to increase investment in digital infrastructure, including broadband Internet systems and facilities for digital transformation, especially in rural and remote areas. A good infrastructure will create a solid foundation for businesses to access and apply technology.

Financial support and tax incentives for green businesses: The government should issue tax incentives for businesses investing in environmentally friendly technology and implement preferential credit packages and financial support funds, specifically for businesses implementing digital transformation. This will not only help businesses reduce their initial investment costs but also encourage them to participate in green economic activities.

Training digital human resources and green skills: It is necessary to develop continuous training programs for human resources, focusing on information technology skills, data management, and knowledge of the green economy. The government should cooperate with educational institutions and businesses to implement short- and long-term courses to enhance the digital transformation capacity of local workers.

Building a cooperation mechanism between localities: To ensure the consistency and effectiveness of digital transformation policies, the government must create a coordination mechanism between provinces and cities, helping to share experiences, resources, and infrastructure in a reasonable manner. Localities can cooperate in joint green economy projects by applying advanced digital transformation technology.

Promote international cooperation and acquire advanced technology: The government needs to expand cooperation with international organizations, donors, and developed countries in the field of green economy and digital transformation. International financial, technological, and knowledge support sources can help Vietnam access sustainable and advanced digital transformation models, thereby promoting rapid regional development.

Policy implications for businesses

Investing in green and environmentally friendly technology: Businesses must actively seek and apply advanced, environmentally friendly technologies to optimize production processes and minimize impacts on the ecosystem. This not only meets the requirements of sustainable development but also helps businesses improve their market competitiveness.

Building a comprehensive digital transformation strategy: Businesses need to build a specific digital transformation strategy from defining goals and processes to choosing appropriate technology. It is necessary to consider sustainability and environmental protection factors in the strategy to ensure that the digitalization process not only improves performance but also contributes to green economic goals.

Training internal human resources: To adapt to digital technology and new processes, businesses must invest in

training employees in green economic and technological skills. This may include short-term training courses, workshops, or partnerships with educational institutions to enhance workers' professional qualifications.

Cooperating with green supply chain partners: Enterprises should seek partners in the supply chain who share the same commitment to sustainable development and green technology applications. By cooperating with suppliers and partners with equivalent standards, enterprises can minimize risks and costs in the digital transformation process while meeting market requirements for sustainability.

Conduct communication and raise public awareness: Enterprises need to proactively communicate the benefits of digital transformation and the green economy not only to employees but also to the surrounding community. This will help raise social awareness of sustainable development while building a better image for the enterprise, creating business advantages, and attracting the attention of investors.

Conclusion: Digital transformation towards a green economy in Vietnam requires close coordination among all levels of government, enterprises, and the community. Supportive policies from the government, combined with the initiative and commitment of businesses, will help this sector overcome challenges and move towards sustainable development goals. Vietnam not only needs supportive policies, but also a comprehensive, synchronous, and consistent development strategy between localities and economic sectors. Implementing these policy implications will help build a solid foundation for a green, adaptive, and developing economy in the context of increasingly severe climate change.

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